

Study about Dharmapuri Caste Violence on 7th November 2012 in Natham Village with Reference to Schedule Caste/Schedule Tribe Prevention of Atrocities Act 1989

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ABSTRACT

Caste system in India is so universal, that no field in India would be complete without referring to it. It is one of the important systems in India which divides people from birth into different caste. A.L. Kroeber defined caste as "an endogamous and hereditary". Sub division of an ethnic unit occupying a post of superior or inferior rank or social esteem in comparison with other such subdivision". The evil of Caste system is that it shows great deal of unjust to mankind the caste system divides itself from Brahma into Bhramans, Sathriyas, Vysnavas, Sudras (according to Hindu mythology). Throughout the years India has gone into many transitions independently, economically, politically but not in caste discrimination one such incident is Dharmapuri caste riot on 7th November 2012. A small love affair between a higher caste girl and lower caste boy which destroyed a village, the background is not just a intercaste marriage but a political parties atrocities.

A Quan-Qual mixed method is used to for the research study which involves the affected families of the Natham village who are the victims of Dahramaburi caste riot. In this method the researcher used sequential explanatory strategy method. The sequential explanatory strategy method is a straight forward technique for the mixed methods approaches. It is characterized by collecting quantitative data analyzing it with qualitative data; the two data are integral part of the study. The researcher adopted mixed method procedure as explained by Creswell (Cresswell, 2013). The objectives 1 to 5 were studied through quantitatively and additionally objective 4 and 5 were studies qualitatively

According to the data acquired all the respondents have suffered economical backwardness by losing their properties, 100% of the respondent have not got justice towards their violence under the SC/ST Prevention of atrocities Act 1989 amended in 2015, this is not the first time were an crime against SC/ST is not given justice, according to the RTI filed by the researcher there has been 207 cases filed under the SC/ST Prevention of the atrocities act 1989 but only 45 cases have been given verdict, in which more than half of the cases have not even taken up for first trial

According to the data collected qualitatively the respondent have quoted that there has been no help from the judiciary system because even after an FIR filed under the SC/ST POA 1989 back in November there has been no trial since then, which shows their negligence towards justice of SC/ST people, according to the data collected the research shows that the people of Natham, Dharmapuri from schedule caste community have not got justice towards their injustice, an according to the study Schedule Caste/Schedule Tribe Prevention Of Atrocities ACT 1989 is not effective towards their caste violence .

Key words: Caste System, Atrocities, Social Justice, Manudharmam.

INTRODUCTION AND METHODOLOGY

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and hereditary”. Sub division of an ethnic unit occupying a post of superior or inferior rank or social esteem in comparison with other such subdivision”. The evil of Caste system is that it shows great deal of unjust to mankind the caste system divides itself from Brahma into Bhramans, Sathriyas, Vysnavas, Sudras (according to Hindu mythology). Throughout the years India has gone into many transition independently, economically, politically but not in caste discrimination one such incident is Dharmapuri caste riot on 7th November 2012. A small love affair between a higher caste girl and lower caste boy which destroyed a village, the background is not just an intercaste marriage but political parties atrocities.

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The research study was a mixed method, hence the results from both the Quantitative and qualitative data are integrated together in the discussion. The qualitative findings are used to enrich the quantitative findings, and the will give a deeper understanding to the phenomena. A common thread in the discussion would be the highlight the factors about the atrocities faced by the victims of Dharmapuri caste violence, and effectiveness of SC/ST PoA Act 1989 towards the case filed

1. Significance of the socio- demographic findings related to the respondents
2. Physical atrocities faced by the victim/respondents
3. Economical atrocities faced by the victim/ respondents
4. Social capital affected because of the caste violence
5. Rehabilitation provided by the government towards the victims
6. Judiciary response towards the violence faced by the respondents

FINDINGS

Socio-economic conditions

The respondents (56%) are from the age group of 30-40 years of age, Among the 50 respondent 80% of the respondents are male and 20% of the respondents are female. The main reason for the majority of the respondents being male is because most of the household leadership was with men and only few women headed house hold fell

into criteria, Education brings about development and urbanization which helps the Dalits to cease depending on upper caste landlords for livelihood. In this research the respondents from Natham village only 6% of the respondents have completed under graduation, and only 4% have completed higher secondary, the majority of the respondent that is 36% are said to be illiterate, 20% has completed primary education, 18% have said to completed middle school and 16% have said to have completed high school

Family is the primary source from which knowledge is passed on from one generation to another, and also family is the first support system which gives care, protection, security and a sense of belonging to each member of the family, from the data that has been collected from the respondents it is said that 25% of the respondents are from nuclear family setup and 23% being joint family and 2% of the respondent are with extended family

The main reason for getting low income is that according to the available data from the respondent the majority of the respondent are illiterate which leads them to work in the unskilled sector which will provide them with low wages, only 5% of the respondents have monthly income between; above 10,000 to 30,000 rupees and only 2% of the respondent have income between 30,000 to 50,000 per month. One of the main reason being the majority of the respondent have income below 10,000 rupees is because they work in the unskilled sector and will get only seasonal work such as working in fields and in paper marts.

According to the data collected from the respondent's majority of 40% of the respondents go for daily wages; based on the findings the respondents feel that they don't get paid enough for the work they do in fields which led them to seek jobs in urban setup; most of the respondents work in Bangalore paper marts to earn money, 6% of the respondent go to work in private companies, and 4% of the respondents work in agricultural sectors were they get land for

lease and practice farming. This data shows that the majority of the respondent move toward urban area for seeking jobs to sustain their family economically

According to the data collected from the respondents, majority of the respondents that is 94% of them are living in concrete house, 2% of the respondents are living in kutch house, and 4% of the respondents are living in semi kutch house. According to the findings from the research most of the respondents got money from the government as a part of rehabilitation towards the violence against them, by the provision under the Schedule Caste/Schedule Tribe Prevention of Atrocities Act 1989, because of that rehabilitation money most of the respondents have concrete house. All of the respondents are from Hindu religion and from Schedule Caste, they main reason for the caste violence is because they are from the Schedule caste community

Atrocities faced by the victim/respondents

According to the data collected from the respondents 24% of the respondents were subjected to physical violence, 22% of the respondents were subjected to verbal abuse during the violence, 66% of the respondents felt that they were economically abused because their properties were vandalized and were severely damaged, and 68% of the respondent felt that their social status and social process in their neighbouring community were destroyed and their reputation was damaged because of the caste violence; why majority of the responded have said no to physical violence(76%) and verbal violence(78%) was because the higher caste community wanted only to damage their properties and bring their economical and social status down. As many as 47,338 cases as been filed all over in India regarding caste violence under SC/ST prevention of atrocities act, this is been recorded in LOK Sabah in the year 2016 (Times Of India, 2018), the state of these acts are miserable,

the law was created to uplift the lower community members to come up in life, to taste equality but this article is a constant reminder that the judiciary system is sure taking its time to bring justice upon the cases which leads most of the time for the cases to be withdrawn. According to the data collected 2% of the respondents were subjected to physically assaulted, 52% of the respondents were assaulted by using explosive substances, 46% of the respondents were assaulted by using chemical explosive substances. These types of assault are punishable crime under S /ST prevention of atrocities act 1989, were when the violence is proven the offender should be imprisoned for minimum 6 month to maximum 5years along with fine. Though the law provides punishment and security towards the protection of the schedule caste and schedule tribe people; there has been rise in crimes towards SC/ST caste people. From the qualitative study the respondents have spoken regarding their social process is that the upper caste people always wants them to be their slaves as the quote *"they always want us to be their slaves till we die"* and regarding their economical violence they have spoken saying that *"I lost my entire house but got only 50,000 as compensation"* which shows that the victims lost everything but got only little as compensation. According to the data collected 35% of the respondents houses were completely damaged during the caste violence and 15% of the respondent's house were partially damaged. Various chemical and other explosive substances were used to harm their houses. Because of the condition they were made homeless in their home homeland, all their hard work was lost in a fraction of second along with their house they lost all their belongings and their savings. This situation brought so much economical burden on the victims of the caste violence

Economical atrocities faced by the victim/ respondents

According to the data collected, for 10% of the respondents house hold items

such as television, fridge, washing machine, cloths got damaged and for majority of the respondents that is for 40% of them their entire house hold items got damaged beyond repair like their television, fridge, washing machine, cloths, sofa, two wheeler and gold ornaments got destroyed and stolen, based on the data collected the main aim of this violence is to stop their economical development, because economical development in a schedule caste or schedule tribe member would mean that they are becoming independent from depending upon the higher caste community for work, this independent action means they are becoming independent and are becoming contributors towards economical growth.

From the qualitative data we can see quotes from the respondent saying that *"I lost my entire house but got only 50,000 as compensation"* from which we can learn that the respondents lost their house hold items and their savings in the caste violence and the government has given only little compensation money for rehabilitation.

Social capital affected because of the caste violence

Social capital is very much important for the growth of the nation but one element which stops social capital networking is caste system, and the main route which destructs social capital is caste related violence, one such case is only Natham caste violence on 7th November 2012, here according to the data collected we can see that 92% of the respondent feel that they have lost their worth and dignity because of the caste violence, 64% of the respondent feel that they don't have proper positive social process because of the violence they are in constant fear that they will be subjected to again, 78% of the respondents their social co-operation has been affected, 32% of the respondents feel that the unity of their community with others have been affected because of the caste violence, and 76% percentage of the community feel that their reciprocity towards other community has not been affected according to the qualitative data

received as spoken by the respondents we can see that the participants felt that the upper caste people always wanted them to be their slaves “ *they always want us to be their slaves till we die*” and the participants have quoted that they felt worthless because of being born a Dalith “ *I often ask god why was I born as a Dalith*” regarding positive social process the participant have quoted saying “ *we don’t participate with other caste people as much as we were before*” so from the study we can understand the negative effect in social process because of the caste violence.

Rehabilitation provided by the government towards the victims

As a part of rehabilitation fund 24% of the respondents have only received 50,000 as their rehabilitative fund, 38% which is majority of the respondents have received 1,000,00 as relief fund and 28% of them received 3,000,00 rupees has their rehabilitative fund and 10% of the victims did not receive any fund for their rehabilitation . the rehabilitation money will be distributed in parts that is if an FIR is filed under SC/ST POA Act 1989 an amount will be issued than for charge sheet they will receive an amount later when the judgement is given they will receive another amount for compensation but here we can see that the victims have received amount only for the FIR filed they did not receive any amount because for the case the charge sheet has not been filed , and even after seven years not even once the case has been called for a trial in special court.

From the qualitative analysis we can see that the respondents have quoted saying “*they government people did not calculate are loss correctly*” because of which we can see victims not receiving proper compensation for their loss and also we can see that the respondent have quoted saying that “*people who gave bribes to government officers got more compensation*” this statement explains about how government officials have used the people vulnerability for their personal benefit

Judiciary response towards the violence faced by the respondents

According to the data collected from the respondents 68% of them have gone to the police station to complain regarding the caste violence which took place on 7th November 2012 in Dharmapuri, Natham village and only 24% of the respondents have FIR copies in hand. And from the other available data we can see that 47% of them have filed for charge sheet and only 21% of the respondents have the charge sheet in hand. These documents are important piece of evidence, this paper prove that there has been such incident performed towards the Schedule Caste and Schedule Tribe, and the information in the FIR and charge sheet plays an primary role in investigation of the case.

The reason for which only few people have taken steps to get justice is because as data collected from the qualitative analysis as spoken by the participants “*the police were rude to us*” this situation is common in most of the SC/ST cases because the police will threaten the victims and put cases in other acts and also we can see how the police have threatened them by booking cases on their children “*They filed case on my son name saying that he is a terrorist*” along with this we can also see statement from the participants that the police making false allegation to prevent them from pursuing any cases “*Police took some of our community men and arrested them saying they have weapons with them*”

CONCLUSION

From comparing both the studies regarding the effectiveness of the SC/ST (PoA) ACT, 1989 we can see that the state and the judiciary system as not taken steps according to the Act in order to preserve the rights of the Schedule Caste, based on the study we can see a lot of negligence from the government and from the judiciary system towards the victim of caste violence which happened in Dharmapuri; this shows that still caste based discrimination still

happens in India and there is not much effect measures produced by the SC/ST (PoA) Act 1989 regarding this caste violence.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. A, P. (1999). Story of Eight Saints Reformers. Publication Division, Government of India.
2. B.R.Ambedkar. (2006). Mr. Gandhi and the Emancipation of the Untouchables. Critical Quest.
3. D.R.Jatava. (2007). violation of human rights. Jaipur : ABD Publishers.
4. india, c. o. (2016). The Schedule Castes and the Schedule Tribes(Prevention of

- Atrocities) Act, 1989. new delhi: universal's.
5. Mirror. (2018, june 14). lynching.
6. ndtv. (2015, august 15). independence day telly caste.
7. Sivakumar S. (2017). death of dalth youth ruled s sicide. dharmaburi: the wire.

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